
AMBEDKAR'S VISION OF EDUCATION: A HISTORICAL SURVEY

Dr Lella Karunyakara

Professor/Director

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, Sidho-Kanho Murmu Dalit and Tribal Studies Centre
Mahatma Gandhi Antarrashtriya Hindi Vishwavidyalaya, Wardha, Maharashtra, India

Abstract: Education for the Dalit community is the most effective means of empowerment. This article aims to critically evaluate Ambedkar's contribution to the educational empowerment of Dalits from the historical perspective. It tries to contextualize education within the Dalit empowerment narrative.

Keywords: Ambedkar, Dalit, Education, Empowerment.

Introduction

Ambedkar found the principles of liberty, equality and fraternity in the philosophy of the Buddha in the form of Prajna (wisdom to understand superstition), Karuna (compassion) and Samata (equality). These three principles of Buddhism appealed to Ambedkar. Hence, he preferred Buddhism as his religion. The aim of Ambedkar's vision of education is to inculcate wisdom - to differentiate between right and wrong; compassion- towards fellow humans and belief in social equality- among students. Ambedkar believed that only with education the Dalits could make progress. He felt that education was important not only because it would help Dalits to get government jobs, but it was equally essential for gaining social and political awareness to protect their rights. In one word the aim of Ambedkar's vision of education is to spread enlightened ideas among the people for the reconstruction of the society on the principles of liberty, equality, fraternity and justice. His famous message was 'Educate, Agitate and Organise'.

Educational institutions founded by Ambedkar

Ambedkar took many initiatives for the educational empowerment of Dalits. On 14 June 1928, he founded Depressed Classes Education Society, Bombay which was also known in Marathi as Dalit Education Society. Under the Dalit Education Society, he established hostels in Panvel, Thane, Nasik, Pune and Dharwad for high school students belonging to Dalit community. On 8th July 1945, he founded People's Education Society, Bombay. Under the People's Education Society, he established Siddharth College of Arts and Science, Bombay in 1946. Soon several educational institutions were set up under the patronage of this society such as Siddharth Night School in 1947; Milind Mahavidyalaya, Aurangabad in 1950; Siddharth College of Commerce and Economics (1953), Milind Multipurpose High School in 1955 and Siddharth College of Law in 1956.

Bahishkrit Hitakarini Sabha (1924)

On July 20, 1924, Ambedkar founded Bahishkrit Hitakarini Sabha¹ with the following aims:

1. To promote the spread of education among the Dalits by opening Hostels;
2. To promote the spread of culture among the Dalits by opening libraries, social centres and classes of study circles;
3. To advance and improve the economic condition of the Dalits by starting Industrial and agricultural schools.

Memorandum for educational empowerment of Dalits (1928)

Ambedkar on behalf of Bahishkrit Hitakarini Sabha submitted a memorandum to the Indian Statutory Commission in 1928 (famously known as Simon Commission). He demanded the government to initiate following educational measures for the Dalit empowerment same on the lines of Hunter Commission's Report of 1882 for the educational development of Muslims:

1. That the special encouragement of Dalit education be regarded as a legitimate charge on local, on Municipal, and on Provincial funds.
2. That higher English education for Dalits, being the kind of education in which that community needs special help, be liberally encouraged.
3. That where necessary graduated system of special scholarships for Dalits be established to be awarded (a) in primary schools (b) in middle schools, (c) on the results of Matriculation and First Arts examinations, and in colleges also.
4. That in all classes of schools maintained from public funds a certain proportion of free studentship be expressly reserved for Dalit students.
5. That, where necessary, the Normal Schools or classes for the training of Dalit teachers be established.

Ambedkar's vision of Primary education

Ambedkar was very much firm that primary education provides Dalits with the necessary foundation to enter into public life as a qualified and well-informed member of society. Hence, he felt that out of all material benefits, Education should be treated as the greatest material benefit. Participating in the Bombay Legislative Council debates on 12th March 1927, Ambedkar viewed primary

education as an enabling mechanism by which an individual can be literate forever. He said, “the object of primary education is to see that every child that enters the portals of a primary school does leave it only at a stage when he becomes literate and continues to be literate throughout the rest of his life.”²

Ambedkar calculated that the rate of dropout prevailing at that time was 82% in primary education. Based on the statistical evidence, he pointed out, “we find that out of every hundred children that enter a primary school only eighteen reach the fourth standard; the rest of them, that is to say, 82 out of every 100, relapse into the state of illiteracy.”³ Hence, he warned that without primary education the Indian society would remain to be largely an illiterate society.

What is the remedy for the school dropout problem of Dalit children? Ambedkar was of the firm view that the government should spend sufficient money on educating society, particularly on primary education. Ambedkar said, “I, therefore, request the Honourable Education Minister to spend more money on primary education...unless we spend a sufficient amount of money, to see that every child that enters schools reaches the fourth standard, what we have already spent him is of no purpose whatsoever.”⁴ The Annual dropout rate of Scheduled Castes in School education according to Educational Statistics at a Glance published by Government of India in 2016 is as follows: Primary 4.14%; Upper Primary 4.38%, Secondary 18.66%, & Senior Secondary 1.81%.

Ambedkar on Commercialisation of Education

Ambedkar criticised the government for making education into business by collecting heavy fees from students. He felt that a major portion of the expenditure on education i.e., 31 to 36 per cent was collected from the students by way of fees resulted in the commercialisation of education. Hence, he argued for affordable quality education. He said, “Education is something which ought to be brought within the reach of everyone. The Education Department is not a department which can be treated on the basis of quid pro quo. Education ought to be cheapened in all possible ways and to the greatest possible extent. I urge this plea because I feel that we are arriving at a stage when the lower orders of society are just getting into the high schools, middle schools and colleges, and the policy of this department, therefore, ought to be to make higher education as cheap to the lower classes as it can possibly be made.”⁵

Source of finance of Education

Instead of collecting the fee from students, Ambedkar suggested the government to spend the money collected from the excise duty on education. Ambedkar as a member of Legislative Council of the Bombay Assembly in 1927 made a historical appeal for grants for the education sector in the Bombay Presidency. While participating in the debates of the Bombay Legislative Assembly he pleaded the government by making a strong argument in favour spending more money on the education sector not only for Dalits and also for all sections of the society.

Government’s budget allocation to education has always been negligible in comparison to other fields. Generally, the government argument is that due to lack of revenue, sufficient funds can’t be provided to education. Spending on education doesn’t give revenue to any society. We may argue that education makes a person into a qualified, well informed valuable citizen of society. Since it is a long-term benefit and not immediate benefit, no political party makes quality education as an issue for winning the elections. Hence, no government wants to spend money on improving the quality of education in government schools and colleges.

Ambedkar had a convincing argument for government spending on education. He said, “We should at least spend on education the same amount we take from the people in the form of excise revenue. The amount of expenditure that we incur per individual in this Presidency on education is only 14 annas, but the amount of money that we recover in the form of excise revenue is Rs. 2.17. I think it is only fair that our educational expenditure should be so adjusted that we should spend on the education of the people as much as we take from them in the form of excise.”⁶

Even today this argument is still valid very much. In the form of indirect taxes like the excise duty, now it is GST Dalits are contributing to the revenue of the government but in return, the educational benefit that they receive from the government is not in proportionate to what they pay. Indeed, governments should spend money on education proportionate to the money collected in the form of GST.

The minimum requirement is the spending of at least 6% of GDP on education. But India spends only 4.6% of GDP. This is the main reason why government educational institutions don’t find a respectable place among the top educational institutions in the global ranking. The government shouldn’t think that there is no money for Dalit education. Dalits are paying for their education through Goods and Service Tax.

How to get Equal Educational Opportunity?

Ambedkar found the great disparity in the comparative advancement in the education of the different communities. He felt that there was a need for comparing the advancement of the different communities in the matter of education. Based on the census report, he found that Dalits are more in population to Brahmins but in education far behind them because of not giving opportunities to Dalit education. How to make Dalits par with Brahmins in the field of education?

Ambedkar noted, "I must here emphasize that this country is composed of different communities. All these communities are unequal in their status and progress. If they are to be brought to the level of equality, then, the only remedy is to adopt the principle of inequality and to give favoured treatment to those who are below the level. There are some I know who object to this and adhere to the principle of equal treatment. For I honestly believe that equality of treatment of people who are unequal is simply another name for indifferentism and neglect. My only complaint is that Government has not yet thought fit to apply this principle to the backward classes. Economically speaking or socially speaking, backward classes are handicapped. I, therefore, think that the principle of favoured treatment must be adopted in their case."⁷ Today his argument is still relevant as it supports the principle of equality of opportunity.

Importance of Hostel facility for students

Majority of the Dalit students in urban areas live in slums and in rural areas in undeveloped surroundings where we could find more liquor shops than schools and libraries. Being born in families live in an evil set of surroundings, Dalit students become easy prey to all sorts of evil influences. Without proper direction, they succumb and give up their education. Hence, Ambedkar wanted hostel facility to all Dalit students. He wanted the government to open more hostels with library facilities for the promotion of the education of the Dalits. Ambedkar felt, "A hostel, first of all, weans the boy from evil surroundings. It provides effective inspection."⁸

Ambedkar was interested in private agencies opening hostels for Dalit students. He said, "... and when a hostel is managed by a private agency, it will mean some saving of money to the government."⁹ Today there are many private companies involve in corporate responsibility towards the society. Unfortunately, we don't find any private to open free hostels for Dalit students under corporate social responsibility which gives even tax exception.

Higher Education

Ambedkar made deliberated on the Bombay University Amendment Act in Bombay Legislature and also made written evidence before the University Reforms Committee in 1925 to express his views on higher education viewed the University as a corporation of scholars. In 1926 he proposed ten universities all over India including one in Karachi. He wanted an integrated course of UG and PG in the University. Ambedkar felt that there was no use to develop higher education without developing primary education for Dalits. On 29 October 1942, Ambedkar submitted a memorandum to the Governor-General on the 'Grievances of the Scheduled Castes' in which he argued for providing education to Dalits in science and technology to develop job skills. Even today, the enrolment of Dalits in professional and technical courses remains less than 10 per cent of the total enrolment.

Dalit Women Education

Ambedkar viewed education for Dalit women as a means for Dalit women empowerment. It makes them live as independent free persons. Ambedkar knew that Dalit women particularly rural Dalit women were vulnerable to all kinds of discrimination and worst forms of violence due to racism, casteism and gender inequality born out of patriarchy. On 18th July 1927, Ambedkar addressed a meeting of about three thousand women, where he made a historical statement about his vision for Dalit women empowerment. He measured the progress of a community by the degree of progress which women had achieved. In other words, educated woman means educated community.

Message to students

Ambedkar's message, "My appeal to students is that after acquiring education, instead of doing some clerical job, he should serve his village or locality people, by which exploitation and injustice arising out of ignorance can be stopped. Your emancipation lies in the emancipation of society."¹⁰

Conclusion

Ambedkar visualized Dalits to shift their knowledge culture from oral tradition to written word culture and to defeat casteist forces with the text. The ultimate aim is to create a Dalit intellectual class in society. But at the same time as a nation builder, he visualized an educated India to construct an empowered India. To realize his dream of building an educated India, he ensured constitutional provisions for educational empowerment of not only Dalits and also all Indians. Constitution of India consists of provisions like - Article 45 that provides free and compulsory education to all and according to Article 46, the state is mandated to safeguard educational interests of Scheduled Castes.

References

1. Keer, Dhananjay. (1971). Ambedkar Life and Mission, Mumbai, Popular Prakashan, p.54-55.
2. Moon, Vasant (Ed.). (1982). Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar: Writings and Speeches, vol.2, Bombay, Government of Maharashtra, p. 40.
3. Ibid, p. 40.
4. Ibid, p. 40.
5. Ibid, p. 40-41
6. Ibid, p. 39-40.
7. Ibid, p. 42.
8. Ibid, p. 44
9. Ibid, p.44.
10. Ambedkar's Agra address delivered on 18 March 1956 quoted in Dalit Voice, August, 1990, 1-5.